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Level of Awareness on Corporate Social Responsibility Among Food Business Establishments

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Abstract

This study determined the level of awareness of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) among food business establishments in Abuyog, Leyte. A survey questionnaire was used to gather data from 12 food business establishments in the year 2026. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics (frequency counts, percentages, and average weighted means). Results showed that CSR awareness among food business establishments in Abuyog, Leyte, remains relatively low, still emerging, with most initiatives driven by government programs and external organizations rather than internal business strategies. To enhance awareness and implementation, stronger collaboration between local government, educational institutions, and business owners is needed, alongside training, incentives, and community-based projects that make CSR both practical and rewarding for small enterprises.

Keywords: Corporate Social Responsibility, External Organizations, Food Business Establishments, Government Programs, Level of Awareness, Stronger Collaboration